

Reconceptualizing Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC): Towards a New Model for the Digital Age

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ABSTRACT: The concept of Integrated marketing communications (IMC) has dominated the study of marketing communications since the 1990s. IMC is the strategic management processes of using customer information to create a unified message and integrate communication mix elements to connect with target customers. The communication mix elements include advertising, direct marketing, sales promotion, public relations and publicity, personal selling, digital marketing communications, etc. However, as digital technologies have evolved through the past decades especially the Internet in the mid 1990's, the model and concepts of integrated marketing communications need to be revisited and revised to reflect the actual situation and two-way communication environment in which we are currently using. This paper reviews the original definition and proposal of integrated marketing communications and then the researcher will outline the reasons for the needs to reconceptualize IMC and to come up with a new model which reflects the digital aspects of marketing communication since the previous model ignores this significant development. Moreover, previous research findings on the effectiveness of IMC are also investigated.

KEYWORDS: Integrated marketing communications, digital marketing, advertising, communication mix elements